

Effect of some inhibitors on the corrosion of mild steel in supply water[†]

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Inhibitive effect of various acid anions as corrosion inhibitor for mild steel in supply water has been studied. Molybdate ion is found to be an effective inhibitor under different operating conditions. The inhibitive effect is due to the blocking of the anodic sites of the metal by adsorption which follows Freundlich adsorption isotherm. Activation energy and other thermodynamic parameters for adsorption have been calculated.

Metals when immersed in aqueous solution tend to corrode due to their thermodynamic instability. Chloride, sulphate and nitrate ions are aggressive from corrosion point of view. Because of the widespread use of mild steel in cooling water systems and industries, the studies of its corrosion is of much interest. The application of corrosion inhibitors holds prominent place amongst other protective methods. Molybdate as corrosion inhibitor for mild steel¹ and for stainless steel² has been reported.

In the present study an attempt has been made to study the corrosion of mild steel in laboratory supply water (SW) and its inhibition by some acid anions.

Results and Discussion

Evaluation of inhibitors : The performance of different acid anions, like sodium cinnamate, disodium hydrogen phosphate, sodium silicate and sodium molybdate as corrosion inhibitors were tested at room temperature ($30 \pm 2^\circ$) except where otherwise stated. The inhibition efficiency of all the inhibitors was found to be excellent providing more than 95% protection. Due to the maximum inhibitive efficiency shown by molybdate ion amongst the inhibitor tested, it was selected for further studies under different operating conditions in supply water.

Effect of inhibitor concentration : The inhibitor concentration in supply water is shown in Fig. 1. The metal-loss progressively decreased with a rise in the concentration of molybdate. The potentials were also ennobled in the presence of inhibitor. The shift of open-circuit potential in the positive direction in presence of inhibitor indicates the interference of the inhibitor with anodic partial process³. There is no quantitative relationship between percentage inhibitor efficiency and shift in potential in the positive direction.

Effect of period of immersion : Weight-loss of metal for

various periods of immersion (5–30 days) in SW with or without inhibitor shows that the longer the period of immersion the greater is the weight-loss; both in presence and absence of inhibitor. Different concentrations of inhibitor (0.03, 0.05 and 2%) were used. Molybdate was found effective in long test duration providing good percentage of protection. 100% protection was recorded by 2% molybdate in all the cases tested.

Effect of temperature : The dissolution of metal increases

Fig. 1. Effect of inhibitor concentration on weight-loss and potential of mild steel in SW (for one month) : (O) weight-loss and (x) potential.

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with rise in temperature (30–80°) both in presence and absence of inhibitor. The inhibition efficiency falls with increase in temperature in all the cases indicating weak (physical) adsorption. The activation energies were calculated from the slopes of Arrhenius plots for uninhibited and inhibited systems. The values are found to be 9.57 kJ mol⁻¹ in SW, 19.4 kJ mol⁻¹ for SW + 0.03% molybdate and 23.93 kJ mol⁻¹ for SW + 0.05% molybdate. It is apparent that the activation energy is higher in presence of inhibitor and increases with inhibitor concentration. The adsorption of inhibitor molecule causes an increase in the activation energy of the process⁴.

Nature of adsorption of inhibitor : To examine the adsorption behaviour of the inhibitor, the data has been fitted to Freundlich adsorption isotherm equation. A straight-line plot supports Freundlich adsorption isotherm.

Other thermodynamic parameters like heat of adsorption, free energy of adsorption and entropy of adsorption along with surface coverage (θ) have been calculated⁵ (Table 1). The negative free energy values for adsorption show interaction of inhibitor molecule⁶ and spontaneous adsorption on the metal surface⁷⁻⁹. The value of heat of adsorption is relatively small, which indicates that the adsorption of inhibitor occurs easily and may be of physical type¹⁰. Increase in activation energy in presence of inhibitor and small values of ΔG are also indicative of physical adsorption of the inhibitor on the metal surface⁹.

Table 1. Values of surface coverage and other thermodynamic parameters of adsorption for corrosion of mild steel in supply water for 30 days containing 0.05% molybdate

Temp °C	Surface coverage	ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	Q kJ mol ⁻¹
30	0.7953	21.06	54.15	
40	0.7906	21.68	54.40	
60	0.7586	22.56	53.78	4.65
80	0.7494	23.76	54.13	

It can be concluded that acid anions tested as inhibitors are good inhibitors providing more than 95% protection. Molybdate ion, which has been studied in detail, shifts the open-circuit potential towards the positive (more noble) di-

rection. The inhibitor is also effective at higher temperature (upto 80°) and in long test duration. The inhibitor reduces the corrosion rate by changing the potential at metal/solution interface by adsorption which follows Freundlich adsorption isotherm. Strong interaction on the corroding metal surface is accomplished by the negative free energy of adsorption.

Experimental

The metal panels (thickness 18SWG, size 5 × 2.5 cm) of mild steel (C, 0.26; Mn, 0.47; Si, 0.089; S, 0.049, P, 0.04%) were used. The composition of supply water used were : TDS, 422 ppm; chloride (as Cl⁻), 16.1 ppm, sulphate (as SO₄²⁻), 11.4 ppm; total hardness (as CaCO₃) 218 ppm; pH, 7.82. Other experimental details were the same as described earlier¹¹.

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